
Physics-informed time-series forecasting of perovskite photoluminescence stability

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Abstract

We present a physics-informed time-series forecasting algorithm designed to predict the long-term photoluminescence stability of metal halide perovskites. Through training on a large experimental dataset of alloyed nanocrystals, the hybrid CNN-LSTM model forecasts long-term stability using only short-term input data. This approach outperforms naïve benchmarks and enables a pathway to reduce experimental testing times. Furthermore, the physics-based featurization ensures intrinsic interpretability, enabling analysis to identify critical stability descriptors for given predictions.

Introduction

The development of new semiconductors is fundamental to enabling advances in optoelectronic devices. This ranges from new detectors suitable for medical applications, to photovoltaic cells for low-cost green energy, and light emitting materials for displays.^[1-3] To this end, new chemistries are investigated in research labs across the globe. Besides characterization of properties after synthesis, validation of long-term stability marks a major milestone towards the widespread application of new materials.

Metal halide perovskites (MHPs) have been at the frontier of this research for more than a decade, with outstanding demonstrations for a range of optoelectronic applications.^[4-6] Despite performances often surpassing those of their established counterparts based on Si, applications are thus far mostly limited to non-industrial cases.^[7] This is in large parts due to their low intrinsic stability under operating conditions.^[8] Consequently, improving stability is one of the most critical challenges in the development of these materials.

As the stability requirements, e.g. for photovoltaic applications, are on the order of 20 years, multiple strategies have been employed to accelerate this process.^[9] Most prominently, testing under increased stress conditions, e.g. elevated temperatures or humidity, is used.^[10] However, resulting test cycles may still be on the order of months and degradation mechanisms at higher temperatures may not be present at typical operating conditions.

As previously highlighted by our group, parallel testing may indeed result in a higher throughput, unlocking large experimental data sets of altered materials properties under

degradation.^[11] However, for highly optimized materials, long test cycles may still mark a major bottleneck for iterative improvement.

Time-series forecasting algorithms trained on experimental data sets may offer a clear pathway to reduce testing time and maintain stress conditions close to those found in applications. Here, historical degradation data can be used to train a model which predicts long-term trends from short-term data. Similar approaches have been most recently explored for battery stability predictions.^[12] However, fully data-driven approaches typically come at the expense of explainability, thereby limiting trust and usefulness in these models and their predictions.

In this work, we employ a combination of physics-informed featurization of experimental data and time-series forecasting to accelerate the research of metal halide perovskite (MHP) material stability. Using a custom-built high-throughput platform designed for the optical characterization of multiple samples during degradation,^[11] we previously acquired large experimental data sets from high-entropy alloyed (HEA) MHP nanocrystals.^[13] To bridge the gap between experimental data and forecasting, we developed an automated spectral segmentation algorithm to extract physically meaningful, time-resolved features from photoluminescence (PL) spectra. Using a forecasting model based on a combined convolutional neural network (CNN) and long-short-term-memory (LSTM) architecture, we clearly outperform native predictions especially over longer input times. The physics-informed approach results in an intrinsically interpretable model that allows to use SHapley Additive exPlanations (SHAP) to identify the most important physical parameters underpinning PL yield stability.

Results & Discussion

Figure 1 **A)** Representative time-dependent PL spectra acquired for two individual samples under continuous degradation. **B)** Overview of evolution for the PL area under curve for various samples normalized at $t = 0$ h. **C)** Results for automated segmentation of PL features into a high energy (HE) and low energy (LE) feature at various points in time.

In **Figure 1A**, we show the PL traces of two individual samples as a function of ageing time to demonstrate the variance of PL behaviour during degradation. At first, a shift in the

emission maximum is visibly due to the different composition. More interestingly, we also observe a difference in the PL intensity over time. The PL intensity in MHPs is strongly affected by defect densities in the material and can be linked to optoelectronic device properties, such as V_{oc} in solar cells or brightness of light-emitting diodes.^[14] We hence take the area under the PL peak as a quality-measure of our perovskite compositions during ageing. In **Figure 1B**, we show the normalized PL area over time for alloyed nanocrystals used in this work. The temporal evolution of this trend can be quite complex, including increases and decreases of PL areas over time often with non-linear trends.

To extract physically meaningful insights from our spectra, we first developed an automated spectral segmentation algorithm. This algorithm starts by identifying a symmetrical component (Gauss-Lorentz) of the PL emission at the high energy (HE) side. The residual data is then fitted with an asymmetrical peak (Doniach-Sunjic) that corresponds to the low energy (LE) side of the feature. An underlying assumption of this model is PL emission results both from band-to-band as well as trap-assisted recombination pathways, linked to the HE and LE features, respectively. The full spectral fitting routine is reported alongside this manuscript.

Figure 1C demonstrates the automated fits for a representative sample at $t = 0$ h, 47 h, and 92 h. From these fits we could extract 20 physically meaningful, time-resolved features. All fitting parameters were then taken as inputs for our time-series forecasting model, but only the normalized PL area was used as the output for the predictions.

Model training and performance

To be able to learn the behaviour of the PL over time, we use a combination of a convolutional neural network (CNN) and a long-short-term-memory (LSTM) layer (short: CNN-LSTM).^[15-17] CNN-LSTM can thus be named as a hybrid architecture made of convolutional and LSTM layers. The convolutional layers extract local patterns of the time-series and also combine the different features used as input data, while the LSTM part can process the time sequence. The datasets obtained for each sample from the PL are split 8:2 into compositions that are used for training the model and those that are used for testing. The training set is then split again by 8:2 by composition into the training set and validation set. The latter is used to determine the best model for a given set of hyperparameters. We fixed some hyperparameters (learning rate: $5 \cdot 10^{-5}$; batch size: 64; patience: 50; max. epochs: 500) and instead only varied the input and output time frames. The input (here: input interval) is the interval of hours of historical data used for the prediction. The output (here: Δt) is a discrete point in the future that is predicted and defined by its distance to the last point of the input interval. We used a windowing approach, to augment the training and validation datasets: For a given input interval/ Δt setting, the first window starts at $t = 0$ h, the second one at $t = 1$ h, etc. As a result, the model is learning to predict the PL area at the relative distance Δt given a certain input interval and will depend less strongly on the initial value at $t = 0$ h.

Figure 2. A) Learning curve of the CNN-LSTM model for **input intervals of 6 hours and Δt of 12 hours**. B) Validation loss, C) RMSE on the testing data set, and D) $\Delta RMSE$ compared to naïve predictions for varied input **intervals** and Δt .

This mechanism ensures time-invariance, as the model learns based on local temporal relationships rather than the absolute timestamp of the measurement.

In **Figure 2A** we show the training and validation loss for one representative set of input interval: Δt hour of 6:12 exhibiting a final RMSE close to the mean of our grid search. The training loss drops monotonically given by the learning rate and that the validation loss follows it closely. The validation loss reaches a steady state after approx. 30 epochs and the lowest validation loss is found after 42 epochs. We repeated this process for input intervals Δt of 1, 3, 6, 12, 24, and 48 h, each. We then show the best validation loss in a 6×6 grid in **Figure 2B**. Small differences within the grid can be picked up. For instance, models with smaller input intervals and larger Δt tend to perform slightly worse in the validation. Similarly, models with longer input intervals generally perform better during validation. It is worth mentioning that the change in validation loss for different models is also strongly affected by the dataset used. There may be compositions that behave completely different

than the mean of the whole dataset. To ensure the validity of our results, we repeated the training 5 times with different initial train/test splits. The validation losses shown in **Figure 2B** are the average best validation loss of those 5 training cycles and hence represent the dataset well.

The testing of our model is done on the test sets, which are compositions that had not been used during the training. Again, we repeated the testing for all 5 train/test splits and report the root-mean-square error (RMSE) in **Figure 2C** for the entire 6x6 grid. Like the validation loss grid, we find that the model performs better, with larger input intervals and smaller Δt . Again, the testing values are also strongly influenced by the dataset used. It is unclear, if the testing RMSE of our model is reasonable, so we compared it to the naïve benchmark, where the predicted value for a given Δt is simply the last value of the input interval.^[18] Again, this was repeated for all 5 train/test splits and the difference to the model RMSE was calculated (Δ RMSE) and is shown in **Figure 2D**. A value larger than 0 indicates that the model performs better than the benchmark. This is the case for larger output timepoints, where the model can pick up trends within the features. Indeed, it indicates that time-series forecasting is needed to be able to make longer-term predictions.

Explainability of the model

As the forecasting algorithm uses physics-informed features, it is intrinsically explainable. To exploit this feature, we used SHAP to gain more insights into the working model through feature importances.^[19]

Figure 3. SHAP feature importances for the six most important features of the CNN-LSTM time-series forecasting model. The depicted values were calculated from the mean of the input.

As shown in **Figure 3**, the total area under the PL peak (Total_area) and features linked to the fitted HE peak area (HE_peak_amplitude, HE_peak_area, Peak_total_area, Norm_area) dominate the feature importance. Additionally, we find that the high energy peak full-width-half-max (HE_peak_fwhm) is also crucial to forecasting long-term PL stability. This finding is in agreement with the PL spectra shown in Figure 1C, where the total emission

in dominated by the symmetric HE peak and only a small contribution comes from the asymmetric LE feature.

For MHP nanocrystals, the PL FWHM has been reported to be determined by inhomogeneities in the nanocrystal size or structural defects in their core and at the surface.^[20]

As all investigated samples were degraded under the same temperature, the FWHM as a proxy for nanocrystal quality appears crucial for predicting stability of optoelectronic properties.

Summary & Conclusion

In summary, we have established a photoluminescence (PL) forecasting algorithm based on a physics-informed approach. We first demonstrated this method using a diverse data set composed of high-entropy alloyed (HEA) metal halide perovskites.

A clear advantage of the physics-based approach is the inherent explainability of the resulting model. The application of SHAP analysis helps to identify global and common descriptors for PL stability within the feature set. As a result, a direct link back to the underlying physical mechanisms governing material stability is enabled which helps to establish trust in the resulting predictions. This highlights the potential of using state-of-the-art neural networks not only for performance prediction but also to enable new scientific insights from high-dimensional and complex data sets.

While the current results are promising, we anticipate further improvements of model performance through the extension of training data to include a wider range of chemistries and crystallinities.

Code Availability

The python code used in this work is readily available.^[21]

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